

WASE:

Using data and AI to make biological waste-to-energy systems more resilient and efficient

Innovate
UK

BridgeAI

CASE STUDY

WASE:

Using data and AI to make biological waste-to-energy systems more resilient and efficient

Authors:

Will Gambier (WASE)
Giulia Tomba (The Alan Turing Institute)
Stuart Gillespie (Independent Contractor)

Additional Contributors:

Harvey Rutland (WASE)
Razaq Sanni (WASE)

Topic overview

This case study explores how **WASE**, a waste-to-energy technology company, is applying data infrastructure and machine learning techniques to improve the operation of biogas production systems. By combining scientific expertise with better data and AI practices, WASE helps hardware operators detect problems earlier and optimise the performance and resilience of their systems – with the ultimate aim of moving towards greater levels of human-augmented automation. Participation in The Alan Turing Institute's Turing Way Practitioners Hub has supported this work by strengthening WASE's approach to aspects including data handling, operational reproducibility, and responsible innovation in this complex, real-world industrial context.

A highly sensitive biological system

Anaerobic digestion has long been used to convert organic waste into biogas and renewable energy. In principle, it is a mature and proven technology. In practice, however, many waste-to-energy sites operate with limited visibility into what is happening inside their reactors, relying on manual periodic sampling and lab testing to keep systems stable and efficient.

WASE's technology is different in several key aspects. First, WASE's system makes use of a technique called electromethanogenesis to accelerate the production of methane through electrical stimulation of microbes, boosting energy production by 30% compared with traditional anaerobic digestion. Second, the company's compact, modular, 'plug and play' reactor setup allows clients to generate biogas from wastewater and organic waste on site, reducing operational and environmental costs and creating a local renewable energy source. One such client is Hepworth Brewery in West Sussex, which, with WASE's help, has become one of the first fully circular wastewater-to-energy systems, generating 362 MWh per year of net energy and saving 100 tonnes of CO₂ annually.

Third, and most importantly for this case study, WASE is developing biosensing technology to provide real-time updates on biological system status – including the use of AI software to combine these insights with historical and benchmark data. As the company scaled its technology, it became increasingly clear that data – how it is collected, stored and interpreted – is just as crucial to a well-functioning waste-to-energy system as the hardware itself.

WASE co-founder and Head of Automation Will Gambier says: “The biological systems inside anaerobic digesters are highly sensitive, and the bacteria that produce biogas must be fed with organic waste carefully: too much and they can be shocked, as though they’ve got a stomach ache, but too little and they starve. Imagine a food manufacturer that is suddenly putting lots of sugary wastewater into the system because they happen to be making sweet things at that point. Recovery from a shock like that can be slow or even impossible. So understanding how to maintain the right balance requires timely, reliable information – something traditional, manual monitoring approaches often struggle to provide.”

Data-driven optimisation

WASE’s current focus is on improving how their systems are monitored and controlled by making better use of both live operational data and historical laboratory data.

Traditionally, key indicators of digester health are measured through manual sampling and laboratory analysis. While accurate, these tests are slow and labour-intensive, and results are often delivered too late to prevent problems. By the time a result arrives – say, 24 hours later – the system may already be moving towards instability. Some sites may be so remote that timely manual sampling is not even possible.

WASE is exploring how to replace or augment these delayed measurements through the use of software-based ‘soft sensors’: models that infer hard-to-measure biological or chemical properties from readily available online data, such as temperature, gas composition, methane production and, crucially, the unique biosensing insight that their electrodes provide. This allows operators to see warning signs earlier and adjust feeding or operating conditions before failures occur.

Alongside this, WASE is building the data foundations required to support its approach, such as structured databases, cloud-based storage, and interfaces that make information accessible to operators instead of being locked away in disparate spreadsheets or multiple file formats. Even basic dashboard-style reporting can be, as Will puts it, “incredibly useful” for operators in need of quick information.

Building reliable data foundations

A recurring challenge in the waste-to-energy sector is that data exists, but is rarely usable. Operational data – new or historical – may be spread across CSV files, local machines and legacy systems, with little standardisation or visibility.

WASE has invested significant effort in centralising and structuring this data, using cloud infrastructure to store and organise information in a consistent and usable way. This creates a single source of truth for training machine learning models, from which trends can be identified and insights shared with operators. Linked to this is a commitment to reproducibility: WASE Software Engineer Razaq Sanni explains that WASE conscientiously versions its software code, infrastructure, and reporting tools in GitHub so the team can compare or roll back configurations over time, supporting safe and reliable deployment.

Will also highlights data and cyber security as an area that has become increasingly central to WASE's work. Following discussions at Turing Way Practitioners Hub events, the team engaged an external cyber security firm, supported by an Innovate UK grant, to strengthen how data is protected and managed.

AI technology with a human in the loop

One of WASE's most promising developments has been the creation of a soft sensor for a key measurement of waste strength – which indicates how bacteria are likely to respond – known as chemical oxygen demand.

“There isn't a physical sensor for some of these biological metrics, so what we've done is train models on historical lab data and correlate that with live signals like temperature and gas quality,” says AI Process Engineer at WASE, Harvey Rutland. “That gives us a reliable estimate almost in real-time, which is far more useful operationally than waiting a day for lab results.” In trials, this approach has achieved high predictive accuracy for chemical oxygen demand, giving operators visibility of variables that previously required slow lab testing. This capability allows operators to spot risk earlier and reduce feeding rates before the system is overloaded, improving stability and reducing downtime.

At present, WASE's models are used as decision-support tools, and not as autonomous controllers. In line with human-in-the-loop principles, operators remain responsible for making changes to system conditions, using model outputs alongside their own expertise. But with operators often required to balance multiple changing variables at once – something humans are not naturally good at doing reliably – WASE's models provide valuable support for their decision-making by highlighting patterns and risks early.

Over time, WASE is exploring how these models could support a level of automated predictive control, where systems can adjust themselves within defined safety boundaries while retaining model transparency and human oversight.

“The goal isn’t to replace people,” says Will. “These systems are incredibly biologically complex, and operators are already doing a very difficult job with limited information. What we’re trying to do is give them better data and earlier warnings, so they can make better decisions – not to take them out of the loop.”

Challenges: System variability, data quality, and organisational barriers

The inherent variability of biological systems poses one of the biggest challenges to the WASE team’s ambitions. Anaerobic digesters behave less like machines and more like living organisms, making them difficult to model and control reliably. “Every site behaves slightly differently,” says Razaq. “So the challenge is making sure the model is robust enough to be useful across real operating conditions and not just in ideal scenarios. That’s why we’re training on real-world data and focusing on signals that are good enough to act on – rather than perfect – with humans still making the final decisions.”

Data quality is another constraint and resource-heavy challenge, with historical datasets (not originally collected for machine learning purposes) requiring careful cleaning and validation before they can be used to train models. WASE uses these cleaned-up laboratory measurements as ground truth, correlates them with live sensor data, and trains models on long operating histories across multiple sites to improve robustness.

There are also organisational barriers: many sites lack the digital infrastructure or skills needed to take full advantage of advanced analytics, and experienced operators who are comfortable with manual processes may be cautious about adopting new tools that appear opaque, complicated or threatening. WASE is addressing this by starting with simple data reporting dashboards and, as discussed earlier in this case study, keeping humans in the loop and designing decision-support tools that complement existing operator expertise.

Next steps: Refining models and moving towards automation

In the short term, WASE is continuing to refine its soft sensor models using data from multiple sites and longer operating periods. Cloud infrastructure built in early 2025 is enabling more systematic experimentation and comparison across systems.

The next phase focuses on extending these tools to support operators' decisions more directly, and carefully testing whether parts of a waste-to-energy system can be adjusted automatically in small trial setups before any wider use.

Longer term, WASE aims to shift the waste-to-energy sector towards more data-literate operations, where insights from sensors and models are routinely used to improve efficiency, reduce failures and maximise renewable energy output. Alongside this, the team's ambition is to be able to offer its AI-enhanced biosensing tools to a broader range of clients – not just those using WASE's own hardware.

Reflections on *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub

“My background is in engineering rather than data science or AI, so the Practitioners Hub has been invaluable in building a network of experts around me. It’s helped me ask the right questions, understand common pitfalls, and learn from people who have already been through similar challenges. The Hub sessions have also helped us develop an internal framework for how we use AI responsibly within the company – we have even formed an AI council that meets regularly to explore topics such as privacy, ethics and the differences between various generative AI tools.”

Will Gambier,
Co-founder and Head of Automation at WASE

Key takeaways

- High-resolution data infrastructure is as critical as physical hardware for system resilience; by centralising disparate streams into a “single source of truth,” WASE transforms legacy anaerobic digestion into a digitally-optimised biological engine.
- Machine learning models can use historical data combined with real-time information gathered by biological soft sensors to provide beneficial system insights – replacing slow laboratory measurements and enabling earlier intervention.
- By implementing human-in-the-loop design, WASE provides a transparent roadmap towards human-augmented automation, empowering operators to manage biological volatility with greater precision and confidence.
- Incremental deployment and transparency help reduce risk and build trust with operators in a traditional sector – particularly as systems move towards increased automation.
- Participation in The Turing Way Practitioners Hub has supported the institutionalisation of responsible innovation and rigorous data handling, ensuring all AI developments are built upon a foundation of industrial-grade reliability.

Contributors and acknowledgements

This case study is published under *The Turing Way Practitioners Hub* 2025–26 Cohort – case study series. The Practitioners Hub is *The Turing Way* project that works with experts from partnering organisations to promote data science best practices. In 2025, The Turing Way team welcomed **Will Gambier from WASE** as an Expert-in-Residence to discuss and share their implementation approaches to data science and AI as well as build additional skills around best practices in responsible, ethical, and collaborative working. We thank them for leading the development of this case study.

The Turing Way Practitioner's Hub was supported by Innovate UK BridgeAI from 2023–2026. BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. The programme bridges the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency, and data privacy, BridgeAI aims to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

BridgeAI is an Innovate UK funded programme, delivered by a consortium including Innovate UK, Digital Catapult, The Alan Turing Institute, STFC Hartree Centre and BSI.

The Practitioners Hub has also received funding and support from the Ecosystem Leadership Award under the EPSRC Grant EP/X03870X/1 & **The Alan Turing Institute**.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub's 2025–26 Cohort was co-delivered by **Arielle Bennett**, Senior Researcher – Open Source Practices and Dr Ann Borda, Senior Research Community Manager. **Stuart Gillespie** is the technical writer for this case study, and others in the series. Léllé Demertzi is the Research Project Manager. **Giulia Tomba** is the Case Study Liaison for this case study.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Malvika Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of 'Experts in Residence' across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with *The Turing Way*, please email: theturingway@gmail.com

Citation

Please cite this publication as:

Gambier, W., Gillespie, S., & Tomba, G. (2026). WASE: Using data and AI to make biological waste-to-energy systems more resilient and efficient. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19130988>

Innovate UK BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. We bridge the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency, and data privacy, we aim to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

BridgeAI is an Innovate UK funded programme, delivered by a consortium including Innovate UK, Digital Catapult, The Alan Turing Institute, STFC Hartree Centre and BSI.

Learn more at bridgeai.net

